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HOW LONG DO WE LIVE? AN ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC FACTORS AND LIFE EXPECTANCY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Long life represents the well-being or better living standard of a nation; as life expectancy has direct link with social welfare, human health and economic development. How long do we live? This paper examined an analysis of economic factors and life expectancy in Nigeria using annual time series covering a period of 35 years, which is between 1990 and 2024. The study used Life Expectancy (LEXP) as the dependent variable whereas Inflation (INF), Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC), Government Expenditure on Health (GEH), and Unemployment (UNEMP) were used as the independent variables. Data were collected from secondary sources and analyzed using Descriptive statistics, Unit root test, Co-integration tests and Error Correction Modeling techniques. The results of the ECM shows that Inflation (INF) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP); GDP per capita (GDPPC) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP); Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has no significant effect on Life Expectancy (LEXP); and Unemployment (UNEMP) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria during the period of study. The study therefore concludes that economic factors significantly impacts on life expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria within the period of study. The study therefore recommended amongst others that policies aimed at boosting GDP per capita, increasing healthcare spending and addressing unemployment especially among the youths are vital for enhancing life expectancy.

Keywords: Economic Factors, Life Expectancy, Unit Root Test, Co-integration, Error Correction Model

Introduction

Health is one of the most important assets a human being has. It permits us to fully develop our capacities. If this asset erodes or it is not developed completely, it can cause physical and emotional weakening, causing obstacles in the lives of people (Monsef & Mehrjardi; 2015). A sine qua non condition of the general well-being

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of the population is health (Tarca, et al. (2024)). The World Health Organization (2006) defines health as “a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not simply the absence of disease or infirmity”. According to Lomborg (2002) in Ali & Ahmad (2016), long life represents the wellbeing or better living standard of a nation; as life expectancy has direct link with social welfare, human health and economic development. Life expectancy, as observed by Bai et al. (2018), has become a common health indicator worldwide and serves as an important measure in public health. It reflects the quality of social life and allows inequality levels and trends to be compared within and across societies.

As observed by Freeman et al. (2020), one of the most important achievements of human society in the last quarter of a millennium is the constant increase in the average life expectancy at birth, in all countries, regardless of the level of development. However, Shaw et al. (2005) noted that there are still significant differences between the developed and the developing world. As a result, life expectancy can have a major positive impact on the main aspects of socio-economic life that takes place in certain country, including female fertility, investment in human capital, health and pension expenditures, and last but not least, economic growth itself (Shaw et al., 2005).

Reports from The Guardian (2025) show that Nigeria has been ranked as the country with the lowest life expectancy in the world; standing at 54.9 years, according to the latest United Nations World population prospects data. The figures show Nigerian men have an average life expectancy of 54.3 years, while women live slightly longer at 54.9 years. This figures places Nigeria at the bottom of a list of 25 countries with the shortest life-spans, ahead only of Chad at 55.2 years and South-Sudan and the Central African Republic at 57.7 years.

Thus, population longevity is an indicator of the human well-being of a country: the most developed countries have a higher life expectancy than other countries (Karma, 2023). Karma noted that the state of health of the people would be conditioned 50% by socioeconomic and cultural factors; the other factors are much less important: environmental factors, genetic factors, and health care.

Several studies (Monsef & Mehrjardi, (2015); Tarca et al (2024); Ali & Ahmed (2016)), amongst others have shown that economic factors significantly affect life expectancy, with higher GDP per capita, increased government expenditure on health, improved education, and improved nutrition generally leading to longer lives; while economic instability like high unemployment and inflation, poverty shorten it.

This paper, therefore aims to examine the short-run and the long-run effects of economic factors on life expectancy in Nigeria. The paper hypothesized that life expectancy would correlate with economic factors such inflation, per capita gross domestic product, government expenditure on health and unemployment rate, all of which have significant impacts on the daily life of the population.

Literature Review

This section covers theoretical literature, conceptual literature and empirical literature review.

Theoretical Literature Review

Mosley and Chen Theory of Child Survival in Developing Countries

The theoretical basis of this paper like in my previous papers is Mosley and Chen (1984) Theory of Child Survival in Developing Countries. Traditionally, social science research on child mortality has focused on the association between socio-economic status and levels and patterns of mortality in populations. Correlations between mortality and socioeconomic characteristics are used to generate causal inferences about the mortality

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determinants. Income and maternal education, for example are two commonly measured correlates (and inferred causal determinants) of child mortality in developing countries population (Mosley & Chen, 1984).

The theory of child survival in developing countries by Mosley and Chen (1984) proposes a new analytical framework for the study of the determinants of child survival in developing countries. The approach incorporates both social and biological variables and integrates research methods employed by social and medical scientists. It also provides for the measurement of morbidity and mortality in a single variable. The framework is based on the premise that all social and economic determinants of child mortality necessarily operate through a common set of biological mechanisms, or proximate determinants, to exert an impact on mortality. The framework according to Mosley & Chen (1984) is intended to advance research on social policy and medical interventions to improve child survival.

The key to the theory is the identification of a set of proximate determinants or intermediate variables that directly influence the risk of morbidity and mortality. All social and economic determinants must operate through these variables to affect child survival. According to Mosely and Chen (1984), the proximate determinants are grouped into five categories:

- i. Maternal factors: age; parity; birth interval
- ii. Environmental contamination: air, food/water/fingers; skin/soil/inanimate objects; insects' vectors
- iii. Nutrient deficiency: calories; protein; micronutrients (vitamins and minerals).
- iv. Injury: accidental; intentional.
- v. Personal illness control: personal preventive measures; medical treatment.

For this study, the theory of child survival is a useful indication that positive improvements in all the proximate determinants will positively affect mortality and morbidity thereby increasing the rate of child survival in Nigeria. A reduction in environmental contamination and personal illness is needed to enhance child survival among under-five children improvement in maternal factors and nutritional deficiency is also needed to balance longevity among under-five children in Nigeria, all things being equal.

Economic Factors

Economic factors refers to variables like inflation, unemployment rates, interest rates, exchange rates, government policies, etc. that influence the national economy of a given nation. According to Freeman (2025), economic factors are economic variables that impact the overall economy, as well as individuals and businesses. They are created by collating and aggregating data from various sectors of the economy. Many economic factors, such as unemployment, exchange rates, inflation, wages, and supply and demand, typically impact how businesses make a profit and increase their efficiency (Indeed, 2025).

Life Expectancy

According to United States Centre for Disease Control (2024), life expectancy refers to the average number of years of life remaining to a person at a particular age and based on a given set of age-specific death rates – generally, the mortality conditions existing in the period mentioned. Human life expectancy is a statistical measure of the estimates of the average remaining years of life at a given age. The most commonly used measure is life expectancy at birth (LEB, or in demographic notation e_0 , where e_x denotes the average life remaining at age x) (Wikipedia).

According to Macrotrends (2025), Nigeria life expectancy for 2025 was 56.36, a 0.54% increase from 2024; Nigeria life expectancy for 2024 was 56.05, a 2.92% increase from 2023; Nigeria life expectancy for 2023 was

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54.46, a 0.71% increase from 2022; and Nigeria life expectancy for 2022 was 54.08, a 1.17% increase from 2021.

Thus, life expectancy at birth indicates the number of years a newborn infant would live if prevailing patterns of mortality at the time of its birth were to stay the same throughout its life.

Empirical Literature Review

Lawal Osinusi & Bisiriyu (2021) studied inflation and life expectancy in Nigeria: granger causality approach. The study focused on the examination of inflation and life expectancy in Nigeria using causality analysis from 1980 to 2019. The study gathered secondary data from World Bank, World Development Indicators Dataset for empirical analysis by adopting the ADF unit root test, VAR autoregressive lag order, and Granger causality test. The results revealed that all the incorporated data are stationary justifying their inclusion for analysis. The Granger Causality result affirmed no causality between life expectancy and inflation rate in Nigeria over the years of analysis while there is unidirectional causality in the other variable (exchange rate) and life expectancy over the period of analysis in Nigeria.

Ataboli, Oniore & Aigbedion (2025) studied the impact of macroeconomic variables on life expectancy in Nigeria (1990-2023) using the autoregressive distributed lag and error correction models. The results show that inflation has an insignificant negative impact on life expectancy in Nigeria. Interest rate has a significant and negative impact on life expectancy in Nigeria; unemployment has an insignificant and negative impact on life expectancy in Nigeria; while exchange rate has a significant and positive impact on life expectancy in Nigeria. Real gross domestic product in Nigeria has a significant and positive impact on life expectancy in Nigeria.

Garcia, Rabago & Ocat (2019) studied predictive capacity of country inflation rate to life expectancy at birth within 120 selected countries. The study utilized an ecological study design where existing data and statistics on inflation rates and life expectancy per country for the years 2017 from World Bank databases were collated. The results indicated that the inflation rate of a country significantly predicts its life expectancy outcomes. The results further revealed an inverse relationship, with life expectancy being lowered by approximately 20% for each unit of increase in the inflation rate.

Bai et al (2018) studied trends in life expectancy and its association with economic factors in the Belt and Road countries-evidence from 2000-2014. The study examined the change in life expectancy (LE) among countries along B&R and studied the impact of economic development on LE. Data from 65 B&R countries from 2000 to 2014 were compiled. Trend of LE was examined by sex and country. Linear quantile mixed model was used to study the association between LE and economic factors. Results revealed that GDP per capita was positively associated with longevity across B&R countries. The unemployment rate was positively associated with LE only for countries in the top LE quantiles. GDP growth rate and inflation were negatively associated with LE for countries in the bottom LE quantiles for men, not for women.

Li et al. (2025) carried out a study on unraveling the determinants of life expectancy during and after the COVID-19 pandemic: a qualitative comparative analysis. The study innovatively employed Qualitative Comparative Analysis with data from 2020-2022, integrating multiple global data sources. Results revealed that environmental quality, represented by access to electricity, consistently emerged as a necessary and sufficient condition across key case scenarios for achieving high life expectancy. Factors such as mean years of schooling, gross national income per capita, urban population density, and measles immunization were found to be

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influential in various combinations within these case, underscoring the complexity of life expectancy determinants.

Ilori et al. (2017) studied an empirical analysis of public health expenditure on life expectancy: evidence from Nigeria using time series data spanning between 1981 and 2014. The study employed recent bounds testing co-integration approach developed within the framework of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) procedure to determine the long-run relationship between public spending on health and life expectancy in Nigeria. Results suggest that a long-run relationship between life expectancy, public health expenditure, primary school enrollment exist in Nigeria. Results further revealed that primary school enrolment and carbon-dioxide emission significantly and directly influenced the rate of life expectancy in Nigeria.

Ali & Ahmad (2016) studied the impact of socio-economic factors on life expectancy for Sultanate of Oman: an empirical analysis. The paper investigated the impact of food production, school enrollment, inflation, population growth, per capita income and CO₂ emissions on life expectancy for Sultanate of Oman using time series data from 1970 to 2012. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach was used in the estimation. The results show that food production, school enrollment has a positive and significant relationship with life expectancy for Sultanate of Oman. On the other hand, inflation and per capita income has negative but insignificant relationship with life expectancy for Sultanate of Oman.

Bao et al. (2022) studied real estate prices, inflation, and health outcomes: evidence from developed economies. The study scrutinizes the impact of real estate prices (housing rent) and inflation on population health by using advanced economies from 1996 to 2019. Health was measured by infant mortality rates and life expectancy at birth. The empirical results show a positive and significant effect of housing rent on the infant mortality rate. In contrast, housing rent improves life expectancy. The results further revealed expectancy. The results further revealed that an increase in inflation positively affects the infant mortality rate and has a negative effect on life expectancy. GDP and health expenditure tend to improve health by increasing life expectancy and reducing the infant mortality rates. Unemployment was harmful to population health.

Aigheyisi (2020) carried out a study on trade openness, foreign direct investment and life expectancy in Nigeria using annual time series data spanning the period from 1981 to 2017. The study employed the ARDL approach to co-integration and error correction modelling. The results show that while import openness adversely affects life expectancy in the country, the effect of FDI inflows is positive, but not significant. Further results indicate that increase in the level of per capita income and government recurrent expenditure in health enhances life expectancy, while inflation adversely affects it.

Onwube et al. (2021) carried out a study on determinants of life expectancy in Nigeria: an autoregressive distributed lag approach from 1981 to 2017. The results show that real GDP per capita, inflation rate at lag 1 and 2, import (lag 1), and government consumption expenditure at lag 1 are positively related to life expectancy in the short-run, whereas current inflation rate, imports, household consumption expenditure (lag 1), exchange rate and exchange rate (lag 1) are inversely related to life expectancy. The long-run results indicated that while real GDP per capita, HCE, and EXR impacted positively on life expectancy, inflation rate, imports, and GCE impacted negatively on life expectancy.

Tarca et al. (2024) studied social and economic determinants of life expectancy at birth in Eastern Europe. The study investigated the effects of GDP per capita (as the economic factor), healthcare expenditure, the number of medical doctors (as social factors), CO₂ emissions (as the environmental factor) on life expectancy. The study

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utilized panel data analysis for 13 Eastern European countries over the 2010 – 2020 periods. The results show that a one percent increase in health expenditure (as % of GDP) increases life expectancy at birth by 0.376 years, whereas each additional medical doctor per 10,000 inhabitants increases life expectancy at birth by 0.088 yearly on average.

Mimi et al. (2024) carried out a study on how economic, health, and environmental and demographic factors affect life expectancy? A novel attempt for developed and developing economies. The study empirically assessed the impact of economic, health, environmental and demographic factors on life expectancy in 36 high-income and 65 middle-income nations from 2000 to 2019. Using panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs) regression; the results show that high-income nations have significantly longer life spans. The factors that lead most to this strengthening include GDP per capita, population growth, financial development, food production, and fertility rates.

Patel (2024) studied analysis of factors influencing life expectancy in developing countries in India. The study adopted a desk methodology by collecting data from existing resources preferably because of its low cost advantage as compared to a field research. The findings of the study revealed that factors influencing life expectancy in developing countries include healthcare access nutrition, sanitation, economic stability, education, and governance. Economic stability facilitates healthcare investments while education and stable governance influence health behaviours and service availability, contributing to longer life spans in these regions.

Methodology

This paper adopted the ex-post facto research design. The choice of ex- post facto was informed by the fact that the numerical data required for the actual empirical analysis was collected from secondary sources.

Model Specification

Life Expectancy at Birth Model

This paper adopted the work of Salatin & Bidari (2014) and Bao et al., (2022) but with some modifications in terms of the variables.

$$LEXP = f(INF, GDP\ per\ CAP, GEH, UNEMP) \tag{3}$$

The ordinary least squares (OLS) form of the equation is written as:

$$LEXP = b_0 + b_1INF + b_2GDPPC + b_3GEH + b_4UNEMP + U \tag{4}$$

$$b_1 < 0; b_2 > 0; b_3 > 0; b_4 < 0$$

- LEXP = Life expectancy at birth
- INF = Inflation rate
- GDPPC = GDP per capita
- GEH = Government Expenditure in Health
- UNEMP = Unemployment rate
- b₀ = Constant
- b₁ –b₄ = Coefficient of explanatory variables
- U = error term

Estimation Technique

This study employed descriptive statistics, unit root test, Co-integration, and Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) modelling techniques to estimate the effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable. To

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ensure that the estimated model is robust and unbiased, the fitness of the model was determined by checking goodness of fit statistics and conducting diagnostics tests.

Result and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 below presents the result of the descriptive statistics of the variables employed in the estimations in this study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Test Results

	LEXP	INF	GDPPC	GEH	UNEMP
Mean	49.72600	18.33257	317609.4	143.2849	14.34000
Median	50.38000	13.01000	226245.0	81.91000	13.90000
Maximum	54.46000	72.84000	1028712.	468.6400	27.40000
Minimum	45.48000	5.390000	5093.070	0.150000	3.500000
Std. Dev.	3.017789	15.66996	308578.0	155.5025	7.699054
Skewness	-0.121868	2.200667	0.766491	0.838774	-0.125980
Kurtosis	1.551519	7.021038	2.391439	2.303994	1.681559
Jarque-Bera	3.146361	51.82987	3.967222	4.810445	2.627582
Probability	0.207385	0.000000	0.137572	0.090245	0.268799
Sum	1740.410	641.6400	11116329	5014.970	501.9000
Sum Sq. Dev.	309.6396	8348.623	3.24E+12	822155.3	2015.365
Observations	35	35	35	35	35

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The result of the descriptive statistics in Tables 1 shows that life Expectancy (LEXP) has a mean value of 49.72600 with a standard deviation of 3.017789. The skewness value of Life Expectancy (LEXP) is negative (-0.121868), meaning that Life Expectancy (LEXP) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis value of Life Expectancy (LEXP) is 1.551519 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Inflation (INF) has a mean value of 18.33257 with a standard deviation of 15.66996. The skewness value of Inflation (INF) is negative (2.200667), meaning that Inflation (INF) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis value of Inflation (INF) is 7.021038 (i. e. greater than 3), meaning that it is leptokurtic. That is, it has a peak distribution, meaning that the series has more value higher than the sample mean.

Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a mean value of 317609.4 with a standard deviation of 308578.0. The skewness value of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is positive (0.766491), meaning that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is 2.391439 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a mean value of 143.2849 with a standard deviation of 155.5025. The skewness value of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) is positive (0.838774), meaning that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Government

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Expenditure on Health (GEH) is 2.303994 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Unemployment (UNEMP) has a mean value of 14.34000 with a standard deviation of 7.699054. The skewness value of Unemployment (UNEMP) is negative (-0.125980), meaning that Unemployment (UNEMP) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Unemployment (UNEMP) is 1.681559 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean. Again, one important observation in this table is the Jarque-Bera statistics of the variables. It shows that the values of INF is greater than 5.99, meaning that they do not have a normal distribution while UFM, LEXP, MAM, GDPPC, GEH and UNEMP has a value less than 5.99, suggesting that they have a normal distribution. Based on these observations, it is therefore necessary to test for the stationarity of the variables and the long run relationship since using the variables at level might give a spurious result. The unit root test is conducted so as to make the variables stationary. The study adopts the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test procedure.

Unit Root Test for Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model.

Tables 2 below present results of stationarity test for each of variables used using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results for Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model)

Variables	ADF at Level	ADF at 1 st Difference	Status	Remarks
LEXP	0.069437	-3.646342	I(1)	Stationary
INF	-2.237259	-4.760123	I(1)	Stationary
GDPPC	1.075593	-7.303771	I(1)	Stationary
GEH	0.326534	-6.316342	I(1)	Stationary
UNEMP	-2.139660	-5.054909	I(1)	Stationary
Critical Values				
1% level	-3.646342	-3.653730		
5% level	-2.954021	-2.957110		
10% level	-2.615817	-2.617434		

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The outcomes of unit root test in Table 2 for the Model, reveals that all the variables were not stationary at level but were stationary at difference. Hence, this study concludes that the variables used in model were integrated of order one, that is I (1). Since the ADF results indicate that the series are of the same order of integration, we proceed to conduct co-integration.

(ii) Co-integration Test Result for Model Two (Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model)

The result of co-integration test for the model is presented in Table 3 below. This will enable us determine if there exists long run equilibrium relationship among variables applied in this model.

Table 3: Co-integration Test Result for Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model)

Unrestricted Co-integration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized	Trace	0.05	Prob.**
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No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Critical Value
None *	0.690537	90.77500	69.81889	0.0005
At most 1 *	0.601384	52.06876	47.85613	0.0191
At most 2	0.378171	21.71676	29.79707	0.3145
At most 3	0.141379	6.038794	15.49471	0.6910
At most 4	0.030104	1.008691	3.841465	0.3152

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Max-eigenvalue)

Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	Prob.**
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Critical Value
None *	0.690537	38.70624	33.87687	0.0123
At most 1 *	0.601384	30.35200	27.58434	0.0215
At most 2	0.378171	15.67796	21.13162	0.2442
At most 3	0.141379	5.030103	14.26460	0.7380
At most 4	0.030104	1.008691	3.841465	0.3152

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The co-integration outcomes in Table 3 above reveals that both the trace test statistics and the max-eigenvalue statistics indicate two (2) co-integrating equation at 5 % significance level. This suggests that there exists a long-run relationship among variables in the model. Accordingly, the study rejects the null hypothesis of no co-integration amongst the variables but accepts the alternative hypothesis.

(iii) Over-Parameterized ECM Estimation Results for Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model)

The result of overparametrized ECM estimation of the Model is presented below.

Table 4: Overparameterized ECM Estimation Results for Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model)

Dependent Variable: DLOG(LEXP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/29/25 Time: 00:21

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2024

Included observations: 32 after adjustments

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Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.003214	0.001869	1.719655	0.1048
DLOG(LEXP(-1))	0.650095	0.285152	2.279822	0.0367
DLOG(LEXP(-2))	-0.153565	0.225892	-0.679815	0.5063
D(INF)	0.000143	0.000135	1.060842	0.3045
D(INF(-1))	-0.000107	0.000111	-0.965181	0.3488
D(INF(-2))	0.000104	8.37E-05	1.244832	0.2311
DLOG(GDPPC)	0.019722	0.009335	2.112671	0.0507
DLOG(GDPPC(-1))	-0.006443	0.009985	-0.645310	0.5279
DLOG(GDPPC(-2))	-0.012054	0.009593	-1.256609	0.2269
DLOG(GEH)	-0.000781	0.002317	-0.336984	0.7405
DLOG(GEH(-1))	-0.002291	0.002173	-1.054604	0.3073
DLOG(GEH(-2))	-0.002303	0.002075	-1.110081	0.2834
D(UNEMP)	0.000184	0.000180	1.018583	0.3236
D(UNEMP(-1))	-5.82E-05	0.000154	-0.378843	0.7098
D(UNEMP(-2))	-0.000194	0.000173	-1.122048	0.2784
ECM(-1)	-0.420360	0.126975	-3.310575	0.0044
R-squared	0.729571	Mean dependent var		0.005290
Adjusted R-squared	0.476044	S.D. dependent var		0.004415
S.E. of regression	0.003196	Akaike info criterion		-8.347073
Sum squared resid	0.000163	Schwarz criterion		-7.614205
Log likelihood	149.5532	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-8.104148
F-statistic	2.877688	Durbin-Watson stat		1.745623
Prob(F-statistic)	0.021772			

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

(iv) Parsimonious ECM of the Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model

The result of ECM estimation of the Model is obtainable in table 5 below.

Table 5: Parsimonious ECM Estimation Results for Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model

Dependent Variable: DLOG(LEXP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/29/25 Time: 00:29

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2024

Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.002284	0.001389	1.644281	0.1143

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DLOG(LEXP(-1))	0.546052	0.160874	3.394282	0.0026
D(INF)	0.000107	7.69E-05	1.393002	0.1775
D(INF(-1))	-0.000167	8.13E-05	-2.049856	0.0325
DLOG(GDPPC)	-0.022931	0.007905	-2.900735	0.0083
DLOG(GDPPC(-2))	-0.017857	0.007201	-2.479729	0.0213
DLOG(GEH(-1))	-0.001155	0.000998	-1.157333	0.2595
DLOG(GEH(-2))	-0.001936	0.001231	-1.572941	0.1300
D(UNEMP(-2))	-0.000253	0.000130	-1.944538	0.0447
ECM(-1)	-0.584643	0.150090	-3.455426	0.0009
<hr/>				
R-squared	0.686814	Mean dependent var	0.005290	
Adjusted R-squared	0.558692	S.D. dependent var	0.004415	
S.E. of regression	0.002933	Akaike info criterion	-8.575283	
Sum squared resid	0.000189	Schwarz criterion	-8.117241	
Log likelihood	147.2045	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-8.423455	
F-statistic	5.360639	Durbin-Watson stat	1.850448	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000631			

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

From Table 5, it shows that the explanatory variables included in the model explained about 56 percent of variation in life expectancy in Nigeria as shown by Adjusted-R² of 0.558692. The remaining 44 percent is explained by the error term. The F-statistic of 5.360639 with a prob.value of 0.000631 shows that the model is statistically significant; and that independent variables are significant explanatory factors of the dependent variable. The above implies that model has a goodness of fit and Durbin Watson Statistic of 1.850448 reveals that there is minimal serial autocorrelation among variables used in model. Also, the Error correction coefficient (ECM) is statistically significant and appropriately signed. This reveals that secondary school enrolment in Nigeria adjust to changes in explanatory variables by about 58 per cent annually.

Furthermore, From Table 11, the result of the short run estimation shows that Inflation (INF) has a negative (-0.000167) relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP), suggesting that a unit increase in Inflation (INF) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP) by 0.000167 units in Nigeria. The negative effect of Inflation (INF) on Life Expectancy (LEXP) confirms to a priori and therefore is line with economic theory. The coefficient of Inflation (INF) is statistically significant at 5 percent level in the short run. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INF) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) but do not reject the alternative hypothesis in the short run.

Both current and past lag 2 of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a negative (-0.022931 and -0.017857, respectively) relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP), suggesting that a unit increase in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) decreases Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria. The negative effect of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) on Life Expectancy (LEXP) does not conform to a priori and therefore not in line with economic theory. The negative effect of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) on Life Expectancy (LEXP) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects

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the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis.

Past lag 1 and 2 of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a negative (-0.001155 and -0.001936, respectively) relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP), suggesting that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) decreases Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria. The negative sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) on Life Expectancy (LEXP) do not confirm to a priori and therefore not in line with economic theory. The negative sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) on Life Expectancy (LEXP) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) in the short run.

While Unemployment (UNEMP) has a negative (-0.000253) relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP), suggesting that a unit increase in Unemployment (UNEMP) decreases Life Expectancy (LEXP) by 0.000253 units in Nigeria. The negative sign of Unemployment (UNEMP) on Life Expectancy (LEXP) confirm to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The negative sign of Unemployment (UNEMP) on Life Expectancy (LEXP) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Unemployment (UNEMP) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis.

(v) Post Estimation Test for Life Expectancy (LEXP) Model.

The researcher conducted a diagnostic test to determine whether or not series were free from order autocorrelation (Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test) and heteroscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test).

The outcome of the diagnostic tests is presented in Table 11 below.

Table 6: Ramsey Reset Test, Serial Correlation LM Test and Homoscedasticity Test Results for Model Two (Life Expectancy (LEXP)Model)

	F-Statistic	Prob. Value
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	1.081296	0.3582
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	0.674236	0.7235

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

From Table 6, the outcome of autocorrelation test using Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM method showed F-statistics is 1.081296 with a Chi-Square probability value is 0.3582. This indicated that probability value of about 36 percent (0.3582) is larger than 5 percent (0.05) critical value; hence confirmed no serial correlation in model.

Again, result of heteroscedasticity test using Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test showed the F-statistics is 0.674236 and a Chi-Square probability value is 0.7235. This suggested no evidence of heteroskedasticity in model since Chi-square probability value of about 72 percent is more than 5 percent ($p > 0.05$). So, residuals do have constant variance which is desirable in regression denoting that residual are Homoscedastic.

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Discussions

Inflation and Life Expectancy in Nigeria

The study reveals that Inflation (INF) has a negative relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP). This means that a unit increase in Inflation (INF) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Inflation (INF) is statistically significant at 5 percent with Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria within period of study. The study therefore rejects null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INF) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria but do not reject the alternative hypothesis within period of study. This means that Inflation (INF) significantly reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria.

The negative findings of this study agree with the works of Ataboli et al. (2025) who found that Inflation is identified as a barrier to maintaining healthcare investments, with downstream effects on life expectancy.

GDP per capita and Life Expectancy in Nigeria

The ECM result reveals that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a negative relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP). This means that a unit increase in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) decreases Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is statistically significant with Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria within period of study. The study therefore rejects null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria but do not reject the alternative hypothesis within period of study. This means that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria. This result is in line with Bai et al. (2018) who found that despite rising GDP per capita, some countries experienced stagnation or decline in life expectancy, especially among disadvantaged groups.

Government Expenditure on Health and Life Expectancy in Nigeria

The study reveals that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a negative relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP). This means that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) decreases Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) is not statistically significant at 5 percent with Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria within period of study. The study therefore accepts null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria. This means that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) do not have any significant effect on Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria.

The findings of this study disagree with the works Ilori et al. (2017) who found that effective government health expenditure is associated with improved health outcomes, including life expectancy.

Unemployment and Life Expectancy in Nigeria

The study reveals that Unemployment (UNEMP) has a negative relationship with Life Expectancy (LEXP). This means that a unit increase in Unemployment (UNEMP) decreases Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The coefficient of Unemployment (UNEMP) is statistically significant at 5 percent with Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria within period of study. The study therefore rejects null hypothesis as there is no significant

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relationship between Unemployment (UNEMP) and Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria but do not reject the alternative hypothesis within period of study. This means that Unemployment (UNEMP) significantly reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria.

The findings of this study disagree with the works of Bai et al. (2018) who found that Persistent unemployment correlates with long-term health declines and reduced life expectancy. That Unemployment significantly worsens public health outcomes, including reductions in life expectancy.

Conclusion

The results of the ECM shows that Inflation (INF) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP); GDP per capita (GDPPC) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP); Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has no significant effect on Life Expectancy (LEXP); Unemployment (UNEMP) reduces Life Expectancy (LEXP) in Nigeria during the period of study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- i) Policies aimed at boosting GDP per capita, increasing healthcare spending and addressing unemployment especially among the youths is vital for enhancing life expectancy.
- ii) Since inflation negatively affects life expectancy, government should place a greater priority at reducing inflation, most especially food inflation.
- iii) Fiscal and monetary policy measures aimed at stabilizing prices should be prioritized by the government having known its significance on life expectancy.

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